

Temple of 'Athtar dhū-Qabḏ

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Entry tags: Archaeological monument, Religious Group, pre-Islamic South Arabian religion, Religious Place, Temple

This imposing religious edifice was built in the late 5th century BCE in the sacred area within the ancient South Arabian urban site of Yathill (now uninhabited and known as Barāqish, present-day Yemen). It was dedicated to the god 'Athtar dhū-Qabḏ, supreme deity of the Minaeans, the people who inhabited the Jawf valley of ancient Yemen during the first millennium BCE and who also occupied this settlement from the 6th century onward. This temple was built later than the adjoining one dedicated to the god Nakrah, with which it shares some design elements, such as the entrance staircase, the imposing propylaeum made of monolithic pillars more than six meters high, a hypostyle room divided into five naves and here organized into four inner cenacles. However, the differences are also significant: the adyton here features a central cella with two large accessory rooms on either side, and it is also possible that there was an upper floor, which made this building sensibly bigger than the adjoining one. Although the temple has been reused since antiquity, partly collapsed and then also heavily looted, the excavations made it possible to appreciate the grandeur of its layout and the refinement of its interior furnishings, as for the four decorated offertory tables placed inside the cenacles. The first reuse occurred shortly after the end of the Minaean kingdom, around the first century CE, by the Arabian Amīr tribe, who nevertheless continued to use the temple for religious purposes, rededicating it to their god Ḥalfān. Excavations have unearthed dozens of inscriptions written in ancient Minaic, a South Arabian language of the Semitic phylum, as well as a few other pieces written in Sabaic, esp. in the Amiritic variety. The area of this building was occupied continuously for different purposes from the early Islamic period until the 17th-18th centuries CE, when the site was abandoned indefinitely.

Date Range: 600 BCE - 100 CE

Region: Barāqish

Region tags: Yemen

This is the current name of the site, which corresponds to ancient Yathill, a Minaean urban settlement within the Jawf valley, the region where the pre-Islamic South Arabian kingdom of Ma'in flourished.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: A. Agostini, 2021, "Il tempio di 'Athtar dhu-Qabḏ. Lo scavo". In: S. Antonini & F.G. Fedele (eds.), *Barāqish/Yathill (Yemen) 1986-2007. Volume 1: Excavations of Temple B and related research and*

restoration / Scavi del Tempio B e ricerche e restauri connessi. Oxford: Archaeopress, 2021 ISBN 978-1-78969-470-3. pp. 95-150.

– Source 2: 16. A. A. Agostini, 2015, "The excavation of the temple of 'Athtar dhu-Qabḍ in Barāqish. Stratigraphic data and historical reconstruction". Proceedings of the Seminar for Arabian Studies 45, pp. 1-14

– Source 3: A. de Maigret, 2010, "The excavations of the Italian Archaeological Mission at Barāqish (Republic of Yemen)", Newsletter Archeologia 0, pp. 55-59.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1989-1992 / 2002-2008

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Missione Archeologica Italiana nella Repubblica dello Yemen / Italian Archaeological Mission to the Republic of Yemen (MAIRY)

Topographical Context

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Terracing

– Water feature

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:
Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?
– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:
– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:
– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

- ↳ A single structure
– Yes

- ↳ The structure has a definite shape
– Rectangular

- ↳ A group of structures:
– No

- ↳ A group of features:
– Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
– Yes

- ↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
– Yes

- ↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

Notes: The temple could have various functions besides general worship, such as offerings and atonements.

- ↳ Worship:
 - Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

Notes: Probably yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
 - Yes

- ↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed
 - Collapsed

- ↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:
 - Other [specify]: Part of the structure was pillaged in ancient times and the rest probably later collapsed due to abandonment.

- ↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:
 - Human-caused accident
 - Natural phenomena

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

- ↳ In antiquity
 - Periodically

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: The area on which the temple was erected had been occupied for different purposes, sometimes reusing the surviving structures of the temple.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: God ‘Athtar dhu-Qabḍ

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The building was re-dedicated to the god Ḥalfān, once the temple was occupied by the intrusive Arabian Amīr tribe.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

Notes: The building of the temple was commissioned by Waqih’īl Riyām King of Ma‘īn and the Assembly of Ma‘īn (according to the inscription Y.05.B.B.13).

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Notes: The works have been supervised by Ya'ws'īl son of Yasma'īl dhū-Ġazīr Saḥfān (according to the inscription Y.05.B.B.13).

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: It is possible that the erection of a temple dedicated to the supreme Minaean deity was consequent to an increased role of the city of Yathill within the Minaean political structure discernible from the 6 cent. BCE onward.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– Field doesn't know

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Notes: These structures are in fact part of a same building project and they are deeply connected to each other (i.e. monumental staircase, propylon, and body of the temple).

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 180

Notes: This estimate is calculated on the size of the outer sides of the main body of the temple (the hypostyle hall).

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 6.15

Notes: This is the maximum height of the pillars of the entrance propylaeum. Four of the original six are perfectly preserved and still in situ and form the tallest element of the building. The pillars of the hypostyle room measure 5.5 m (four of the original 12 are preserved).

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Field doesn't know

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The limestone employed in the building probably came from nearby, but the actual quarry has never been identified.

- ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
 - No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

- ↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
 - Yes

- ↳ On the outside:
 - Yes

- ↳ On the inside:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries
 - Yes

- ↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

- ↳ Are there gods depicted:
 - No

- ↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:
 - No

- ↳ Are there humans depicted:
 - No

- ↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Ibexes on the offertory tables

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: Dentils

↳ Floral motifs

– No

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: Inscriptions are engraved on the interior walls of the building, on some interior furnishings (offertory tables), and on other movable objects.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably not.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: animal (ibex)

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Red pigment was found on the inscribed surface of the interior walls, but this is unrelated to any figurative pictorial representation.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

Notes: Generally, the Ancient South Arabian inscriptions were also appreciated for their intrinsic decorative values, but this was not the main purpose of the writing action.

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: The main typology of the inscriptions found in situ are: commemorative, legal, and ritual.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Field doesn't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

Notes: The ibexes that are present in some decorated objects, like the offertory tables, may have been associated to the sacral dimension, but they unlikely were used to represent supernatural beings.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– No

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Field doesn't know

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: A stela with a personal name was found during excavations, but it is unclear whether it should be considered a funerary stela or a votive stela.

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they sky deity:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)
– No

- ↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No
- ↳ Are they kin relation to elites:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are they unquestionably good:
 - Field doesn't know

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ In dreams:
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: Probably yes, but dreams are not clearly mentioned in the documentation from this temple
- ↳ In trance possession:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Texts from the sacral area, to which this temple belongs, mention oracular consultations, so it is possible that some kind of connection with the divine was established.
- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: Probably yes
- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - Field doesn't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

↳ Libations:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Offerings of food:

–Yes [specify]: seasonal products

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human sacrifice:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Sacred objects:

–Yes [specify]: cultic objects

↳ Daily life objects:

–Yes [specify]: e.g. inscriptions; panels; incense burners.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not possible to have a precise answer: we do not know if there were any norms regulating the sexual behavior in general, except for the fact that a sexual act can produce a state of impurity that is not allowed for those who intend to approach the sacred area.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: In the sense that care of personal hygiene can restore that state of purity required for approaching the temple

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Possibly yes, e.g. through requests of oracular consultations.

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– Field doesn't know

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:
– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):
– Yes

Notes: Possibly yes, cf. the obsidian deposit found inside the main cella.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

Notes: See e.g. inscription Y.05.B.B.14

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably yes, in later times the site was destination of a pilgrimage by the tribe of Amīr for their god Dhū-Samāwī (cf. inscription Haram 10).

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Notes: The four seasonal offertory tables inside the hypostyle hall are a good indication at this regard.

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably a central place at this regard had the four cenacles present in the hypostyle room.

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Yes

Divination by examination of the exta:

Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species

– Field doesn't know

Divination through human communication:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably yes, through incubation

Divination through animal-behavior:

– Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

Notes: Very unlikely given the dimension of the building.

Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: According to the size of the hypostyle hall, at maximum capacity there could have been about 50 individuals.

How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: It is possible that the rituals followed a calendar, but at the moment it is not possible to be more precise. Based on the inscriptions on the offertory tables, we can say that there was at

least a seasonal cadence.

- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - Field doesn't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: We can take it for granted that there was the presence of an institutionalized clergy, but the inscriptions do not reveal clear data about their organization, in general within the Minaean realm, and in particular within this temple.

- ↳ Present full time
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Present part time
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:
 - Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably yes

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: Esp. Legal texts, although these cannot be considered in this cultural context totally unrelated to the religious domain.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Notes: The abundant epigraphic material found in the temple falls into the dedicatory, legal, ritual categories, but there are no traces of sacred texts, or "inspired" or literary texts that are the result of a long transmission.

Bibliography

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